

Construction and standardization of toolkit of numeracy skills

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ABSTRACT

India is facing learning crisis as close to 5 crore children in elementary school, lacks numeracy and literacy skills mentioned in draft NEP, 2019. ASER (2021) reported that COVID 2019 has worsen the situation, as only 10 per cent of the kids studying grade III to V in government schools can solve a subtraction problem. National Curriculum Frameworks, time to time has expressed the need to bring changes in the areas of teaching, learning and assessment for qualitative improvement in the school education system in India. If we want to bridge the learning gap, we need to provide the suitable interventions. For that purpose, we need to know where students are on the skill continuum and specifically the learning areas which need attention. Traditional pen paper test or examination is designed to test their knowledge on the bases of content, not on competence.

This paper endeavors to construct standardized a simple, cost effective and easy to administer screening assessment toolkit to check the competence based numeracy skills for grade three.

Final draft of the toolkit is comprised of 9 items. Reliability of the toolkit was found by test re-test method and it was .89. Content validity and construct validity of the toolkit was also established.

Keywords : Numeracy skill, screening toolkit

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Numeracy skill refers to ability to use the mathematical concepts learned in the classroom in all area of life. If students have mastered the Numeracy skill, they will able to analyze the situation critically and will have problem solving capacity. If we want to students to succeeded in their life they should be numerate. Now the question arises, whether our schooling system is

able to impart Numeracy skills amongst the students. If we read the annual status of education report then the situation is very alarming for every educationist. Every year since 2005, ASER has reported on children's schooling status and the inability to do basic reading and arithmetic tasks. At least 25% of school children in the 4-8 age groups do not

have age-appropriate and essential cognitive and numeracy skills, (ASER 2019).

The SLIM study (carried out by Eiland Wipro in 2006) assessed students in India's top schools for their conceptual understanding and found that our top schools don't promote conceptual learning in students. Performance of class 4 was found to be below international level. Students don't know how to apply learnt mathematics skill during classroom in real-life situations. Two third of the students in class 4th could not master the measurement of the length of a pencil with the ruler.

So it is highly required that something must be done in order to bridge the learning gaps in mathematics. In order to provide the early interventions to the students to enhance the learning skills, teacher need to identify the different learning needs of the children that arise due to individual difference. In a year numbers of paper pen tests are conducted to evaluate the students leaning but that proves to a futile exercise as they fail to provide clear cut picture of child's current knowledge and skills. Suppose a child could not answer the statements sums in the question paper or could not solve the few test items, it doesn't mean it may be due to language barrier or due to lack of procedural knowledge or conceptual understanding. Due to COVID 2020 the situation got worse, students who are having the educated parents and having who are having smart phones they could keep up with learning curve but the students who are first generation learner or nor economically well of could not avail the classes from the school and could not get parental support, lacked behind in the learning. Now it is the need of hour to determine their current knowledge continuum. Whether students are performing at par or below the level. If they are performing below the level, what exactly it is. Whether they have small discrepancies, 1 grade below or more. So researcher felt the need of screening tool that can identify the learning gap of the students in Numeracy skills that need attention, so that

their differential need should be met and no child to be left behind.

Construction of toolkit

Objective: - To construct and standardize a screening toolkit for grade 3 to assess the proficiency level of students for the Numeracy Skills in Mathematics.

Development and standardization of toolkit

This toolkit is going to be designed to assess the learning gap of the student. Learning gap of the student can be assess if the designer of the toolkit know , what are the learning outcome expected from the child of 8 years old and studying in grade 3. So the researcher consulted the subject teacher teaching grade 3, consulted the learning outcomes lead by NCERT. After knowing the expected learning outcomes of Indian students, the researcher has gone through the latest trend in assessment and studied the various toolkit EGMA (Early Grade Mathematical Assessment) and ACARA (Australian Curriculum Assessment and reporting Authority). In accordance to latest trend in assessment and learning outcomes, a toolkit comprises instrument based on Numeracy Skill was designed. The designed toolkit was sent for expert opinion from 5 educators and modifications were made on the basis of their recommendations. Whether the toolkit is conducive for 3 grade students studying in India and to know the difficulty level and discriminating power of the toolkit, the pilot study was conducted in a private school.

Toolkit framework

Task 1 is comprised of manipulation of number. It has four sub tasks.

- ❖ Read the 4 digit numbers,
- ❖ Tell the place value and face value
- ❖ Identify the greater number.
- ❖ Read the Roman number,
It is of 5 marks.

Task 2 is comprised of 10 items. Child has to detect the number pattern and has to tell the

correct missing number. Each correct response will get .5 marks.

Task 3 is comprised of 5 items on addition and 5 on subtraction. The subtraction problems are inverse of addition problem. Each correct answer will get 5 marks.

Task 4 is based on Multiplication and division. 5 items on multiplication and 5 on division are given. Each correct answer will get .5 marks.

Task 5 is containing of 6 world problem based on real life situation. If students solve accurately will get 2 marks each.

Task 6 is based on time. It contains 3 items. It has 3 subtasks. Each subtask is of 1 mark.

Task 7 is based on money. Notes and coins given to child. Child has to arrange the currency to represent the amount given in 5 different subtasks. Each subtask will be of 1 mark each.

Task 8 is based on measurement. Child would be given 3 subtasks. In 1 task child has to measure the length of pencil and it will be of 1 mark. 2 subtasks convert liter into militer and it will be of 1 mark. Subtask 3 is of child has to find out the more capacity. It is of 3 marks, 1 mark for correct answer. 1 mark for correct procedure and 1 mark for accuracy.

Task 9 is based fraction and it has three subtasks and 1 mark for each.

Snapshot of the toolkit

TASK	DISCRIPTION	TIME TAKEN	MARKS	
NUMBER NAMING FLUENCY	20 numbers would be presented to the child. Child would tell the number name	60 seconds	.5 marks for each correct response 0 for each incorrect response X for no response.	RECONSTRUCTED AND MERGE
NUMBER DISCRIMINATION	Child would be presented 10 pairs of numbers. Child has to tell the greatest number.	60 seconds	.5 marks for each correct response 0 for each incorrect response X for no response.	
MISSING NUMBERS	The child has to identify the pattern of the number series and supply the correct numbers.	60 SECONDS	.5 marks for each correct response 0 for each incorrect response X for no response.	
Addition and subtraction	Child would be presented 5 sets of problems on addition; same problems would be presented in-form of subtraction. Invigilator will observe if the child could see the relationship between addition and subtraction. Though the marks would be given on the basis of correct answer even if they could not see the relationship.	60 seconds	.5 marks for each correct response 0 for each incorrect response X for no response.	

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MULTIPLICATION AND DIVISION	Child would be presented 5 sets of problems on multiplication same problems would be presented in-form of Division. Invigilator will observe if the child could see the relationship between multiplication and division Though the marks would be given on the basis of correct answer even if they could not see the relationship.			
WORD PROBLEMS	The child will be provided with 6-word problems. The first child has to read and understand what mathematical operation has to be applied.			
TIME GOES ON	3 questions based on time.	-	1 marks for each correct response. 0 for incorrect response X for no response	
MONEY	The child has to arrange the currency to represent the asked amount by the assessor			
MEASUREMENT	Child will estimate the capacity of water tanks, length of pencil and convert liter into milliliter.			
FRACTION	Three questions would be asked based on fraction.			

Tryout of the toolkit

To find out the discriminating power and difficulty value of the toolkit, it was necessary to conduct pilot study in school. The researcher visited the principal of private school in Ludhiana district and got permission to conduct the study after explains the purpose of pilot study. The study was conducting on 69 students that was studying in class 3. Researcher took meeting of three assessor appointed for pilot study and explain the purpose and procedure of the screening toolkit. Required copies of drafted toolkit were printed and confidentiality was insured. It was administered one to one bases orally. Stopwatch was used for timely tasks.

ITEM ANALYSIS:

Whether the test items are designed according to age level and grade level of the students. It was necessary to select the appropriate tasks by obtaining **discriminating power and difficulty value** of the task to be including in the toolkit. **Kelley (1939) has shown that if we take into consideration, highest performing group of 27% of the total sample, we can confidently say that highest performing groups have better capability in the skills of toolkit than the lowest performing group.**

Discriminating Power (D.P) was calculated by applying formula

$$D.P. = \frac{R_h - R_l}{R_h + R_l}$$

$\frac{N}{2}$
 For computing the Difficulty Value (D.V.) the formula mentioned ahead was used

$$D.V. = \frac{R_h - R_l}{N}$$

Where, R_h = Number of responses of the 27% of the highest performing students.
 R_l = Number of responses of the 27% of the lowest performing students.
 N = sum total number of the both groups.

	TOPICS	DP	DV	
TASK 1	NUMBER NAMING	0.205	0.1025	REJECTED
TASK 2	NUMBER DISCRIMINATION	0.195	0.0975	REJECTED
TASK 3	MISSING NUMBER	0.66	0.33	SELECTED
TASK 4	ADDITION & SUBTRACTION	0.595	0.2975	SELECTED
TASK 5	MULTIPLICATION DIVISION	0.66	0.33	SELECTED
TASK 6	WORD PROBLEM	0.48125	0.240625	SELECTED
TASK 7	TIME	0.6	0.3	SELECTED
TASK 8	MONEY	0.75	0.375	SELECTED
TASK 9	MEASUREMENT	0.39	0.195	SELECTED
TASK 10	FRACTION	1	0.5	SELECTED

Final draft of toolkit

	TOPICS	DP	DV	
TASK 1	NUMBER NAMING & DISCRIMINATION	0.75	0.375	SELECTED
TASK 2	MISSING NUMBER	0.66	0.33	SELECTED
TASK 3	ADDITION & SUBTRACTION	0.595	0.2975	SELECTED
TASK 4	MULTIPLICATION DIVISION	0.66	0.33	SELECTED
TASK 5	WORD PROBLEM	0.48125	0.240625	SELECTED
TASK 6	TIME	0.6	0.3	SELECTED
TASK 7	MONEY	0.75	0.375	SELECTED
TASK 8	MEASUREMENT	0.39	0.195	SELECTED
TASK 9	FRACTION	1	0.5	SELECTED

**Classification of students into four levels according to their Numeracy Skills.
 In achievement, Average = 26.85 and SD=7.69**

CLASS INTERVAL	FREQUENCY
0-10	1
11-20	14
21-30	34
31-40	17
41-50	3

Very Low Performance in Achievement students exist in the interval = (0-18)
 Low Performance in Achievement students exist in the interval = (19-27)
 Average Performance in Achievement students exist in the interval = (28-35)
 High Performance in Achievement students exist in the interval = (36-50)

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ACHIEVEMENTSCORE	CLASSIFICATION
0-18	Very Low Performance in Achievement
19-27	Low Performance in Achievement
28-35	Average Performance in Achievement
36-50	High Performance in Achievement

Reliability

The test-retest method is being used to find out the internal consistency of the test. The reliability coefficient can range from low of zero (negative values are considered zero) to a high of 1.00. In this study test-retest method was used to find out interval consistency of the toolkit. Preliminary draft of toolkit with 9 tasks was conducted twice on 69 students of grade 3 after the gap of 15 days. Then correlation

between both test scores was found by using Pearson's product moment correlation formula. English Literacy for class 3rd was found .92, which indicates that the test is reliable.

Validity

Content validity was established by the opinion of 5 experts. They found the toolkit is designed appropriately considering all aspects of Literacy as per their grade and age. The toolkit does not drift from the operational definition of the

purpose of the study. Construct validity was found by consulting ten experts related to the fields.

Conclusion

This toolkit can be used for students studying in grade 3 in India. It can be used by the teachers, parents, and Pedagogical administrators, who are interested to know the proficiency level in Foundational Skills in English Literacy for the students studying in grade 3. This toolkit will provide a clear-cut picture of the learning gaps of the students which in turn would be helpful to design differential instructions based on the differential needs of the students.

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